

Effect of Cu/Mg ratio on mechanical properties and fracture behavior of SiCp/Al-Cu-Mg composites

Q. Zhang, Q.Z. Wang, B.L. Xiao*, Z.Y. Ma

Shenyang National Laboratory for Materials Science, Institute of Metal Research, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Shenyang, China

* Corresponding author(blxiao@imr.ac.cn)

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Abstract

20vol.%SiCp/Al-Cu-Mg composites were fabricated through powder metallurgy route with different Cu/Mg ratios. The composites were subjected to T4 and T6 treatments, respectively. Yield strength (YS) of the T6 samples were enhanced by increasing the Cu/Mg ratio, however, this was not the case for the T4 samples. The ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of both T4 and T6 samples were independent of the Cu/Mg ratio. The observations of longitudinal sections of tensile specimens indicated that there were cracked SiCp in the longitudinal sections of the T4 and T6 samples, whereas some voids near the SiCp were observed only in the T6 samples. While the YS of the composites with different Cu/Mg ratios was mainly controlled by the strength of the matrix alloys, the UTS was related with the strength of the matrix alloys, the number of the cracked SiCp and the voids of the matrix.

1 Introduction

Particle reinforced aluminum matrix composites (PRAMCs) have received much attentions in the past decades because of their improved strength, modulus, and tribological properties over conventional aluminum alloys [1]. The enhanced performance of the PRAMCs depends on a careful selection of processing technique, the type and size of reinforcing phase, the chemistry of matrix materials, and the heat treatment conditions [1-2]. In the past years, the

influence of particle size, aspect ratio and volume fraction on the mechanical properties of the composites were substantially investigated [1-3].

Al-Cu-Mg, Al-Mg-Si and Al-Zn-Mg-Cu alloys, which have been widely used as structural materials in the aerospace and automotive industry, are usually selected as the matrix materials of the PRAMCs [2-5]. For Al-Cu-Mg alloys, achievement of high hardness and strength is strongly dependent on the type and distribution of hardening precipitates [6]. The previous studies about Al-Cu-Mg alloys suggested that if amount of Cu and Mg concentration was 5wt.%, the alloys contained 4wt.%Cu and 1wt.%Mg exhibited the highest tensile strength after artificial aging. And the precipitates in the alloys were the mixture of θ' and S' [7].

Although the effect of the Cu/Mg ratio on the aging behavior and the strength of Al-Cu-Mg alloys had been widely studied [6-8], few studies were carried out to understand the effect of the Cu/Mg ratio on the microstructure and mechanical properties of the PRAMCs based on Al-Cu-Mg matrix. This inhibits the optimization of the properties of the composites.

In this work, we fabricated 20vol.% SiCp/Al-Cu-Mg composites through powder metallurgy (PM) route with different Cu/Mg ratios and investigated the effect of the Cu/Mg ratio on the mechanical properties and fracture behavior of SiCp/Al-Cu-Mg composites.

Table 1 Compositions of matrix alloy of composites in the present study

Sample Number	Cu (wt.%)	Mg (wt.%)	Al (wt.%)	Cu/Mg weight ratio
1	3.4	1.9	balance	1.8
2	3.7	1.6	balance	2.3
3	4.0	1.3	balance	3.1
4	4.3	1.0	balance	4.3

Fig.1 Variation of yield strength and ultimate tensile strength of composites with the Cu/Mg ratio: (a) T4 samples, (b) T6 samples

2 Experimental

Al-Cu-Mg based composites reinforced by 20vol.% SiC particles with a mean particle size of 7 μm were used in this study. The composition of the matrix alloys were showed in Table 1. All the composites were fabricated through PM technique. The hot pressed billets were forged in an open die using 200 MPa pressure. The total deformation ratio was 4:1. The tensile specimens with a gage diameter of 5 mm and a gage length of 25 mm were machined from the forged billets. The specimens were subjected to T4 (510 $^{\circ}\text{C}/1\text{h}$ solutionized, water quenched, and then naturally aged for 96h) and T6 (510 $^{\circ}\text{C}/1\text{h}$ solutionized, water quenched, and then 170 $^{\circ}\text{C}/16\text{h}$ aged) treatments, respectively, before tests. Tensile tests were conducted on INSTRON 5582 at a strain rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} .

After the tensile tests, the fractured specimens were electro discharge cut in a longitudinal direction along the tensile axis and then polished. The longitudinal sections and fracture surfaces were examined by a scanning electron microscope (SEM, quanta 600). Data of the percentage of cracked SiC particles and other types of damage (e.g. matrix voids) were all collected from SEM micrographs which taken from the area 100 μm below the fracture surface in the longitudinal sections. For example, the number percentage of the cracked SiC particles was the ratio of the number of the cracked SiC particles to the total number of the SiC particles

which collected from at least five SEM micrographs and each micrograph contained at least 200 SiC particles.

3 Results

Fig. 1 shows the variation of yield strength (YS) and ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of all the composite samples with the Cu/Mg ratio. YS and UTS of the T4 samples were independent of the Cu/Mg ratio, whereas YS of the T6 samples are enhanced by increasing the Cu/Mg ratio. However, UTS of the T6 samples were still independent of the Cu/Mg ratio.

Fig. 2 shows the SEM micrographs of tensile fracture surfaces of sample 4. The fracture surfaces of the T4-treated sample exhibited microscopically ductile appearances. Dimples of aluminum matrix and fractured SiCp were visible on the fracture surfaces of the T4 sample. The character of the fracture surfaces of the T6 sample was similar to that of the T4 sample except for that the dimples of aluminum matrix in the T6 sample were shallower than those in the T4 sample. The observations of other samples with different Cu/Mg ratios in both T4 and T6 conditions indicated that different Cu/Mg ratios did not cause an evident change in the tensile fracture surfaces (not shown).

Fig. 3 shows the SEM micrographs of longitudinal section of sample 4 in both T4 and T6 conditions. As shown in Fig. 3, a significant

Fig. 2 SEM fractographs of sample 4: (a) T4, (b) T6

Fig. 3 SEM micrographs of longitudinal sections of sample 4: (a) T4, (b) T6

number of SiCp fractured in both T4 and T6 samples, however there were some voids near the SiCp in the matrix of the T6 sample, which was not visible in the T4 sample. The cracked SiCp could not bear the loading during the tensile test. Meanwhile, if some voids appeared near the SiCp, these particles could not also bear the loading because the loading could not be transferred from the matrix to the particles [10]. So we defined the cracked particles as SiC_c and defined the particles associated with the voids as SiC_v. The percentage of the SiC_c and SiC_v as a function of the Cu/Mg ratio is shown in Fig. 4. For the T4 samples, the percentage of the SiC_c was independent of the Cu/Mg ratio and the number of the SiC_v could be neglected because of quite limited quantity. However, for the T6 samples, the percentage of the SiC_v increased with increasing the Cu/Mg ratio, while the percentage of the SiC_c decreased slightly with increasing the Cu/Mg ratio.

4 Discussions

The strength of the PRAMCs was dependent on many factors, such as the matrix strength, the interfacial strength, the type, size, aspect ratio and distribution of reinforcements and so on [2]. In the present study, the possible variables are the matrix strength and interfacial strength which was caused by different Cu/Mg ratios.

Previous studies indicated that the strength of the Al-Cu-Mg alloys was independent of the Cu/Mg ratios ranging from 4.5 to 1.7 under the T4 condition [7-8], and reached the highest value when the Cu/Mg ratio was about 4 under the T6 condition [6]. In this study, the relation of the YS of the composites with the Cu/Mg ratio under different tempers was consistent with that of the Al-Cu-Mg alloys. This fact was in accord with the research of Wu and Lavernia [9]. They [9] suggested that the strength of the composites was dependent on the strength of the matrix and increased with the increase of the matrix's strength under small strain. Under large strains, some particles could not bear the loading due to the cracking or debonding from the matrix [10]. During the tensile test, the matrix around SiCp must suffer more deformation than the matrix far

from SiCp in order to avoid the formation of voids around the reinforcing SiC particles [4]. So if the ductility of the matrix was not enough, voids would appear in the matrix around SiCp during tensile test preferentially.

For the T4 samples, Figs. 3(a) and 4(a) show that there were almost no voids in the matrix. This indicated that the matrix of the T4 samples was ductile enough to suffer the deformation before the sample fractured. Under this condition, the volume fraction of the SiC_c obeyed the Weibull statistics [11].

$$B = 1 - e^{-V/V_0(\sigma^*/\sigma_0)^m} \quad (1)$$

where B is the volume fraction of the SiC_c, V is the particle volume, σ^* is the average stress acting on the SiC particles, m is the Weibull modulus, and V_0 and σ_0 stand for arbitrary quantities of volume and stress, respectively, which were introduced for dimensional purposes. In this study, the number fraction of the SiC_c in all the T4 samples was identical (Fig. 4(a)). So based on Eq. (1), the stress on the SiC was identical before the sample fractured. And based on the model of Eshelby, the stress on the matrix would be identical. So the UTS of the T4 samples were independent of the Cu/Mg ratio.

For the T6 samples, the matrix's ductility would decrease compared with the T4 samples [6]. The poor ductility of the matrix caused the void formation in the matrix around SiCp preferentially. As mentioned above, if some voids appeared near the SiCp, these particles did not bear the loading because the loading could not transfer from the matrix to the particles and the number of the SiC_c did not obey the Weibull statistics [11].

For Al-Cu-Mg alloys, the strength of the alloys after T6 treatment increased with increasing the Cu/Mg ratio from 1.5 to 4.7 and the ductility of the alloys would decrease with increasing the strength [7-8]. During the tensile test, the lower the ductility of matrix alloy, the larger the probability of the void formation in the matrix near the SiCp is. So the percentage of the SiC_v increased with the increase of the Cu/Mg ratio. The voids of the matrix relaxed the stress

Fig. 4 The percentage of SiC_c and SiC_v as the function of Cu/Mg ratio: (a) T4, (b) T6

on the SiCp and reduced the probability of the crack of the SiCp. Meanwhile, the voids caused discontinuity of the matrix and then reduced the strength of the matrix. In this case, although the strength of the matrix increased with the Cu/Mg ratio, the UTS of the composites were still independent of the Cu/Mg ratio.

5 Conclusions

- (1) The YS and UTS of the T4 samples were independent of the Cu/Mg ratio of the matrix. The YS of the T6 samples was enhanced by increasing the Cu/Mg ratio of the matrix, while the UTS of the T6 samples was still independent of the Cu/Mg ratio of the matrix.
- (2) For the T4 samples, some SiC particles cracked during tension, and the number of cracked SiC particles was almost identical for the composites with different Cu/Mg ratios. For the T6 samples, in addition to the cracked SiC particles, some voids formed near the SiCp. The number of cracked SiC particles decreased while the number of void increased with increasing the Cu/Mg ratio.
- (3) The YS of the composites with different Cu/Mg ratios was mainly controlled by the strength of the matrix alloys. The UTS was related with the strength of the matrix alloys, the number of the cracked SiC particles and the voids of the matrix.

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